

The Effects of the Root Condition on Stiffness and Stability of Drum Deployed Composite Tubular Booms for Spacecraft

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Deployable Tubular Booms in Space

Deployable booms are used in the space industry to extend objects, such as drag sails, sensors, antenna and solar sails.

Deployable tubular booms are characterised as being able to be coiled into a cylindrical geometry when stowed and a long 'C' section when extended.

Surrey Space Centre has successfully used deployable booms to de-orbit spacecraft at the end of their mission life.

Historically manufactured from isotropic materials, composite deployable booms offer improved mechanical and thermal properties.

Deployable booms have been proposed for use as the deployment method and supporting structure of an Earth observation telescope.

Current designs cause the root condition of the boom to flatten, reducing the stiffness. Therefore an investigation to quantify these effects has been undertaken.

1. C. Underwood, A. Viquerat, M. Schenk, B. Taylor, C. Massimiani, R. Duke, B. Stewart, S. Fellowes, C. Bridges, G. Aglietti, B. Sanders, D. Masutti, A. Denis. (2019), InflateSail de-orbit flight demonstration results and follow-on drag-sail applications, *Acta Astronautica*, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2019.05.054>.
2. J. Fernandez, M. Schenk, G. Prassinis, V. Lappas and S. Erb. (2013), Deployment Mechanisms of a Gossamer Satellite Deorbiter, 15th European Space Mechanisms and Tribology Symposium

Beam Model

A beam model was derived to attempt to capture the reduction in stiffness.

The beam model cannot capture the partial restraining at the root condition, but it can capture the change in geometry.

The change in geometry was calculated using the plate partial differential curvature equation, which was solved using the central difference scheme.

$$\partial^2 \kappa_2 / \partial x^2 + \beta^2 \partial^2 \kappa_2 / \partial y^2 = 0$$

Applying a unit load to the end of the beam, the rotational stiffness was calculated by:

$$k_{rot} = FL / \alpha$$

Finite Element Analysis

A finite element model was created in ABAQUS.

The procedure was as follows:

- Deform the boom using the modelled drum
- Apply an equivalent bolt load
- Release previous constraints
- Apply a load to the end to calculate the rotational stiffness

Cylindrical Deployment Drum

Results

Maximum k_{rot} = rotational stiffness of a clamped beam with a uniform geometry along the length.

Beam k_{rot} = rotational stiffness predicted from the beam model.

ABAQUS k_{rot} = rotational stiffness predicted by ABAQUS

Trans. Len. = transition length of geometry from the root.

Conclusions

When a deployable tubular boom is attached to a cylindrical drum:

- There is a large reduction in rotational stiffness.
- The rotational stiffness increases with a decrease in transition length.

The transition length decreases as the transverse modulus increases to resist flattening of the cross section.

The partial restraining at the root condition is crucial to predict the rotational stiffness, making the beam model insufficient.

Future Work

Future work includes:

- Experimental testing to validate the finite element model.
- Utilising a shell model to improve analytical predictions.